

PEER- REVIEWED INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL

***Aarhat Multidisciplinary
International Education Research
Journal (AMIERJ)***

ISSN 2278-5655

Impact Factor :0.948

Bi-Monthly

VOL - II

ISSUES - V

[2013-14]

**C h i e f -
E d i t o r :**

**U b a l e
A m o l
B a b a n**

[Editorial/Head Office: 108, Gokuldharm Society, Dr.Ambedkar chowk, Near TV Towar,Badlapur, MS

$$\Delta\sigma(x) = \sigma(x) - \sigma(x+1), \quad x \geq 1, \quad \dots\dots\dots 2.4$$

Where $\sigma(x)$ denotes sum of the divisors of x :

3. Experiment:

For the numbers 1 to 100 a table has been formulated for (2.1) and following results have been obtained:

4. Theorem: With the help of table 4 (c)

If $\Delta d = k$ then

$$\prod_{i=1}^n (\alpha_i + 1) = \prod_{j=1}^m (\beta_j + 1) + K$$

Where $x = \prod_{i=1}^n p_i^{\alpha_i}$ and $x + 1 = \prod_{j=1}^m q_j^{\beta_j}$

In particular

If $K = 0$

then $\Delta d = 0$

$\Rightarrow x, x+1$ have similar factorization

Proof can be easily seen with the help of table 4(c)

5. Experiment: For the numbers 1 to 100 a table has been formulated for (2.2) and following results have been obtained:

Theorem 5.1:

Value	Behaviour for $x, x+1$	
	$x = \prod_{i=1}^n p_i^{\alpha_i}$	$x + 1 = \prod_{j=1}^m q_j^{\beta_j}$
-2	$\alpha_i = 1 \forall i$ $K = \text{odd}$	$\beta_j = 1 \forall j$ $I = \text{even}$
-1	$\alpha_i = 1 \forall i$ $K = \text{odd}$	For at least one value of $j, \beta_j > 1$
	For at least one value of $i, \alpha_i > 1$	$\beta_j = 1 \forall j$ $I = \text{even}$

$\mu(x)=$

0	For at least one value of i, $\alpha_i > 1$	For at least one value of j, $\beta_j > 1$
	$\alpha_i = 1 \forall i$ K = odd	$\beta_j = 1 \forall j$ I = odd
1	$\beta_j = 1 \forall j$ I = even	For at least one value of j, $\beta_j > 1$
	For at least one value of j, $\beta_j > 1$	$\alpha_i = 1 \forall i$ K = odd
2	$\beta_j = 1 \forall j$ I = even	$\alpha_i = 1 \forall i$ K = odd

Proof can be easily with the help of 4(d)

seen table

6. Experiment: For the number 1 to 100 a table has been formulated for 2.3 and following results have been obtained.

Group Size	Maximum fluctuation
1	64
2	118
4	118
5	18
10	122
20	126
25	132
50	132
100	132

Table 4(a)

Theorem 7.0 If ϕ denotes Eulers function then $\Delta\phi$ is increasing the interval.

Proof can be easily seen with the help of table 4(a) and 4 (f)

7.1 Experiment: With the help of table 4(h) for x (1 to 200) by taking the group size as divisor of x (e.g. 200) 1, 2, 4, 5, 8, 10, 20, 25, 40, 50, 100, 200 following observations have been made:

Group Size	Maximum fluctuation
1	364
2	730
4	730
5	730
8	730
10	730
20	730
25	730
40	730
50	730
100	730
200	730

Table 4(b)

Theorem 8.0 If σ denotes sum of the divisors then $\Delta\sigma$ have maximum fluctuation at group size one and remains constant in other intervals.

Proof can be easily seen with the help of tables 4(b), 4(g) and 4(h).

$$d(x) = \sum_{d/x} 1$$

X	d(x)	$\Delta d(x)$	x	d(x)	$\Delta d(x)$	x	d(x)	$\Delta d(x)$
1	1	-1	36	9	7	71	2	-9
2	2	0	37	2	-2	72	11	9
3	2	-1	38	4	2	73	2	-2
4	3	1	39	2	-6	74	4	-2
5	2	-2	40	8	6	75	6	0
6	4	2	41	2	-6	76	6	2
7	2	-2	42	8	6	77	4	-3
8	4	1	43	2	-4	78	7	5
9	3	-1	44	6	0	79	2	-7
10	4	2	45	6	2	80	9	4
11	2	-4	46	4	2	81	5	1
12	6	4	47	2	-7	82	4	2

13	2	-2	48	9	7	83	2	-8
14	4	0	49	2	-3	84	10	6
15	4	-1	50	5	3	85	4	0
16	5	3	51	2	-3	86	4	0
17	2	-4	52	5	3	87	4	-4
18	6	4	53	2	-5	88	8	6
19	2	-4	54	7	3	89	2	-10
20	6	2	55	4	-4	90	12	10
21	4	0	56	8	4	91	2	-4
22	4	2	57	4	0	92	6	2
23	2	6	58	4	2	93	4	0
24	8	5	59	2	-10	94	4	0
25	3	-1	60	12	10	95	4	-8
26	4	0	61	2	-2	96	12	10
27	4	-2	62	4	-1	97	2	-4
28	6	4	63	5	-2	98	6	0
29	2	-6	64	7	-2	99	6	0
30	8	6	65	4	-2	100	9	7
31	2	-3	66	6	4			
32	5	3	67	2	-4			
33	2	-2	68	6	2			
34	4	0	69	4	-4			
35	4	-5	70	8	6			

Table 4(c)

x	$\mu(x)$	$\Delta \mu(x)$	x	$\mu(x)$	$\Delta \mu(x)$	x	$\mu(x)$	$\Delta \mu(x)$
1	1	2	34	1	0	67	-1	
2	-1	0	35	1	1	68	0	1
3	-1	-1	36	0	1	69	-1	0
4	0	1	37	-1	-2	70	-1	
5	-1	-2	38	1	0	71	-1	-1
6	1	2	39	1	1	72	0	1
7	-1	-1	40	0	1	73	-1	-2
8	0	0	41	-1	0	74	1	1
9	0	-1	42	-1	0	75	0	0
10	1	2	43	-1	-1	76	0	-1
11	-1	-1	44	0	0	77	1	2
12	0	1	45	0	-1	78	-1	0
13	-1	-2	46	1	2	79	-1	-1

14	1	0	47	-1	-1	80	0	0
15	1	1	48	0	0	81	0	-1
16	0	1	49	0	0	82	1	2
17	-1	-1	50	0	-1	83	-1	-1
18	0	1	51	1	1	84	0	-1
19	1	-1	52	0	1	85	1	0
20	0	-1	53	-1	-1	86	1	0
21	1	0	54	0	-1	87	1	1
22	1	2	55	1	1	88	0	1
23	-1	-1	56	0	1	89	-1	-1
24	0	0	57	-1	-2	90	0	1
25	0	-1	58	1	2	91	-1	-1
26	1	1	59	-1	-1	92	0	-1
27	0	0	60	0	1	93	1	0
28	0	1	61	-1	-2	94	1	2
29	-1	0	62	1	2	95	-1	-1
30	-1	0	63	-1	-1	96	0	1
31	-1	-1	64	0	1	97	-1	-1
32	0	-1	65	-1	0	98	0	0
33	1	0	66	-1	0	99	0	0
						100	0	1

Table 4 (d)

X	$\varphi(x)$	$\Delta \varphi(x)$	x	$\varphi(x)$	$\Delta \varphi(x)$	x	$\varphi(x)$	$\Delta \varphi(x)$
1	1	0	35	24	12	69	44	20
2	1	-1	36	12	-24	70	24	-46
3	2	0	37	36	18	71	70	46
4	2	-2	38	18	-6	72	24	-36
5	4	2	39	24	-12	73	72	-48
6	2	-4	40	16	-24	74	36	-4
7	6	2	41	40	28	75	40	4
8	4	-2	42	12	-30	76	36	-4
9	6	2	43	42	22	77	60	36
10	4	-6	44	20	-4	78	24	-54
11	10	6	45	24	2	79	78	46
12	4	-8	46	22	-24	80	32	-22
13	12	6	47	46	30	81	54	14
14	6	-2	48	16	-26	82	40	-42

15	8	0	49	42	22	83	82	58
16	8	-8	50	20	-12	84	24	-40
17	16	10	51	32	8	85	64	22
18	6	-12	52	24	-28	86	42	-14
19	18	10	53	52	34	87	56	16
20	8	-4	54	18	-22	88	40	-48
21	12	2	55	40	16	89	88	64
22	10	-12	56	24	-12	90	24	-48
23	22	14	57	36	8	91	72	28
24	8	-12	58	28	-30	92	44	-16
25	20	12	59	58	42	93	60	14
26	12	-6	60	16	-44	94	46	-68
27	18	6	61	60	30	95	72	40
28	12	-14	62	30	-6	96	32	-64
29	28	20	63	36	4	97	96	54
30	8	-22	64	32	-16	98	42	-18
31	30	14	65	48	28	99	60	20
32	16	-4	66	20	46	100	40	-60
33	20	4	67	66	34			
34	16	-8	68	32	-12			

Table 4(e)

$\Delta\phi(x)$

G.S.	F	G.S.	F	G.S.	F	G.S.	F	G.S.	F
0-2	1	58-60	86	28-32	42	50-55	62	0-25	26
2-4	2	60-62	74	32-36	36	55-60	86	25-50	60
4-6	6	62-64	20	36-40	42	60-65	74	50-75	94
6-8	6	64-66	62	40-44	58	65-70	92	75-100	132
8-10	8	66-68	58	44-48	56	70-75	94	0-50	60
10-12	14	68-70	66	48-52	50	75-80	100	50-100	132
12-14	14	70-72	92	52-56	62	80-85	98		
14-16	8	72-74	44	56-60	86	85-90	112		
16-18	22	74-76	8	60-64	74	90-95	108		
18-20	22	76-78	90	64-68	62	95-100	118		
20-22	14	78-80	100	68-72	92	0-10	8		
22-24	26	80-82	56	72-76	52	10-20	22		
24-26	24	82-84	100	76-80	100	20-30	42		
26-28	20	84-86	62	80-84	100	30-40	42		

28-30	42	86-88	64	84-88	70	40-50	60
30-32	36	88-90	112	88-92	112	50-60	86
32-34	12	90-92	76	92-96	108	60-70	92
34-36	36	92-94	82	96-100	118	70-80	100
36-38	42	94-96	108	0-5	4	80-90	112
38-40	18	96-98	118	5-10	8	90-100	122
40-42	58	98-100	80	10-15	14	0-20	22
42-44	52	0-4	2	15-20	22	20-40	44
44-46	26	4-8	6	20-25	26	40-60	86
46-48	56	8-12	14	25-30	42	60-80	100
48-50	48	12-16	14	30-35	36	80-100	126
50-52	36	16-20	22	35-40	42		
52-54	62	20-24	26	40-45	58		
54-56	38	24-28	26	45-50	56		
56-58	38						

Table4 (f)

	$\sigma(x)$	$\Delta\sigma(x)$	x	$\sigma(x)$	$\Delta\sigma(x)$	x	$\sigma(x)$	$\Delta\sigma(x)$
1	1	-2	35	48	-43	69	96	-48
2	3	-1	36	91	53	70	144	72
3	4	-3	37	38	-22	71	72	-123
4	7	1	38	60	4	72	195	121
5	6	-6	39	56	-34	73	74	-40
6	12	4	40	90	48	74	114	-10
7	8	-7	41	42	-54	75	124	-16
8	15	2	42	96	52	76	140	44
9	13	-5	43	44	-40	77	96	-72
10	18	6	44	84	6	78	168	88
11	12	-16	45	78	6	79	80	-106
12	28	14	46	72	24	80	186	65
13	14	-10	47	48	-76	81	121	-5
14	24	0	48	124	67	82	126	42
15	24	-7	49	57	-36	83	84	-140
16	31	13	50	93	21	84	224	116
17	18	-21	51	72	-26	85	108	-24
18	39	19	52	98	44	86	132	12
19	20	-22	53	54	-66	87	120	-60
20	42	10	54	120	48	88	180	90
21	32	-4	55	72	-48	89	90	-144
22	36	12	56	120	40	90	234	122

23	24	-36	57	80	-10	91	112	-56
24	60	29	58	90	30	92	168	40
25	31	-11	59	60	-108	93	128	-16
26	42	2	60	168	106	94	144	24
27	40	-16	61	62	-34	95	120	-132
28	56	26	62	96	-8	96	252	154
29	30	-42	63	104	-23	97	98	-23
30	72	40	64	127	43	98	121	-35
31	32	-31	65	84	-60	99	156	-61
32	63	15	66	144	76	100	217	115
33	48	-6	67	68	-58			
34	54	6	68	126	30			

x	$\sigma(x)$	$\Delta\sigma(x)$	x	$\sigma(x)$	$\Delta\sigma(x)$	x	$\sigma(x)$	$\Delta\sigma(x)$
100	217	15	137	288	148	174	372	102
101	102	-114	138	140	196	175	270	90
102	216	112	139	336	144	176	180	-366
103	104	-106	140	192	-24	177	546	364
104	210	18	141	216	48	178	182	-154
105	192	30	142	168	-235	179	336	88
106	162	54	143	403	223	180	248	-112
107	108	-172	144	180	-42	181	360	132
108	280	170	145	222	-6	182	228	156
109	110	-106	146	228	-38	183	384	196
110	216	64	147	266	-116	184	188	-148
111	152	-96	148	150	-222	185	336	16
112	248	134	149	372	220	186	320	-40
113	114	-126	150	152	-148	187	360	168
114	240	96	151	300	66	188	192	-316
115	144	-66	152	234	-54	189	508	314
116	210	28	153	288	96	190	194	-100
117	182	2	154	192	-200	191	294	-42
118	180	36	155	392	234	192	336	-63
119	144	-216	156	158	-82	193	399	201
120	360	227	157	240	24	194	198	-270
121	133	-53	158	216	-162	195	468	268
122	186	18	159	378	186	196	200	-265
123	168	-56	160	192	-171	197	465	193
124	224	68	161	363	199			
125	312	184	162	294	6			

126	312	184	163	294	6
127	255	79	164	252	84
128	176	-160	165	168	-312
129	336	204	166	480	297
130	132	-204	167	183	-177
131	336	176	168	360	100
132	160	-44	169	260	-48
133	204	-36	170	308	134
134	240	-30	171	174	-186
135	270	132	172	360	112
136	138	-150	173	248	-124

Table 4(g)

$\Delta\sigma(x)$											
G.S	F	G.S.	F								
0-2	1	68-70	120	134-136	168	0-4	4	132-136	220	75-80	194
2-4	4	70-72	244	136-138	298	4-8	11	136-140	344	80-85	256
4-6	10	72-74	161	138-140	344	8-12	30	140-144	458	85-90	266
6-8	11	74-76	60	140-142	168	12-16	24	144-148	265	90-95	254
8-10	11	76-78	160	142-144	458	16-20	41	148-152	442	95-100	286
10-12	30	78-80	194	144-146	265	24-28	45	152-156	434	100-105	226
12-14	24	80-82	70	146-148	154	28-32	82	156-160	370	110-115	260
14-16	20	82-84	256	148-150	442	36-40	87	164-168	609	115-120	443
18-20	41	86-88	150	150-152	368	40-44	106	172-172	474	120-125	383
20-22	16	88-90	266	152-154	150	44-48	143	176-180	730	130-135	408
22-24	65	90-92	178	154-156	434	52-56	114	180-184	518	135-140	344
26-28	42	94-96	286	156-158	316	56-60	214	188-192	630	145-150	442
28-30	82	96-98	189	158-160	348	60-64	140	192-196	414	150-155	420
30-32	71	98-100	176	160-162	370	64-68	136	196-200	414	150-155	420
32-34	21	100-102	226	162-164	329	68-72	244	0-5	7	160-165	370
34-36	75	102-104	218	164-166	78	72-76	161	5-10	11	165-170	609
36-38	75	106-108	342	166-168	609	80-84	256	15-20	30	170-175	320
40-42	106	108-110	276	168-170	474	84-88	176	20-25	65	175-180	730
42-44	92	110-112	230	170-172	182	88-92	266	25-30	82	185-189	344
44-46	18	112-114	260	172-174	320	92-96	286	30-35	83	190-195	630
46-48	143	114-116	162	174-176	236	96-100	215	35-40	96	195-200	538
48-50	103	118-120	443	176-178	468	104-108	342	40-45	106	0-8	11
50-52	114	120-122	280	178-180	730	108-112	276	45-50	143	8-16	29
54-56	96	122-124	124	180-182	518	112-116	260	50-55	114	16-24	65

56-58	50	124-126	340	182-184	244	116-120	443	55-60	214	24-32	82
58-60	214	126-128	311	184-186	264	120-124	283	60-65	166	32-40	96
60-62	140	128-130	364	186-188	344	124-128	340	65-70	136	40-48	143
62-64	66	130-132	408	188-190	208	128-132	408	70-75	244	48-56	133
64-66	136	132-134	220	190-192	630						
66-68	134	150-160	434	192-194	414						
66-64	214	160-170	609	194-196	264						
64-72	244	170-180	730	196-198	538						
72-80	227			198-200	233						

80-88 256 **180-190** 518 **0-100** 298

88-96 298 **190-200** 630 **100-200** 730

96-104 268

104-112 342 **0-20** 41

112-120 443 **20-40** 96

120-128 383 **40-60** 214

128-136 408 **60-80** 244

136-144 458 **80-100** 298

144-152 445 **100-120** 443

152-160 434 **120-140** 431

160-168 609 **140-160** 469

168-176 483 **160-180** 730

176-184 730 **180-200** 680

184-192 630 **0-25** 65

192-200 584 **25-50** 143

0-10 13 **50-75** 244

10-20 41 **75-100** 298

20-30 82 **100-125** 383

30-40 96 **125-150** 462

40-50 143 **150-175** 609

50-60 214 **175-200** 730

60-70 166 **0-40** 96

70-80 244 **40-80** 244

80-90 266 **80-120** 443

90-100 286 **120-160** 469

100-110 342 **160-200** 730

110-120 443 **0-50** 143

120-130 383 **50-100** 298

130-140 408 **100-150** 462

140-150 458 **150-200** 730

Table 4 (h)

9. REFERENCE

1. Askey R.[1970] (i) An inequality for classical Polynomials” Nederl, Akad wetensch Porc. Ser. A 73 and indag, math, 32,22-25.(II) Orthogonal Polynomials and positivity in studies in a applied mathematics” 6, special functions & wave propagation editors, D-Ludiwing and F.W.J .Oliver, SIAM Philadephia ; 1970, 64-85.
2. Askey R; Gasper G.& Harrisla L.A[1975] “An inequality for Tchebycheff Polynomials and extensions “ J.Approx . Theory,14,1-11. 3.Bateman Harry“ Higher Transcendental Functions Vol. I,II and II ,Mcgraw- Hill Book company .Inc.
4. Chaurasia V.B.L & Gupta Manisha[1997] “ A theorem concerning a product of two general class polynomials and the multivariable H-functions “ Proc. Indian,Acad Sci.Math 107(3) ,271-276.
5. Common A.K.[1987] “ Uniform inequalities for ultraspherical polynomials and Bessel function of fractional order” J.Approx.Theory .49,331-339.
6. Luke.Y.L.[1989] (i) The Special functions and their approximations , vol., I & II 38,319-328.
(ii) Inequalities for generalized hypergeometric function “ J.Approx. Theory .5,41-65.
(iii) Mathematical function and their approximations “ Academic Press, New York.
7. Hardy G.H., LittlewoodJ.E. & Polya G.[1934] "Inequalities", Cambridge Uni. Press, Cambridge.
8. Hardy G.H. & Wright E.M. [1938] "An introduction the theory of numbers oxford.At the clarendon press.
9. Hardy G.H. & Wright E.M. [1938] "An introduction the theory of numbers oxford.At the clarendon press.
10. Hauston J.[1981] "Multiple q-series idetities", Math., 6, 11-22.